

Investigation on the impact of grazers on the island Æbelø

Evaluation and validation of methodologies in
preparation for a subsequent Master's Thesis

Henry Lankes, 12.07.2023

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Introduction

The primary objective of this project is to evaluate and validate the methodology to investigate the impact of fallow deer (*Dama dama*) and mouflons (*Ovis aries musimon*) on Æbelø, a small island located north of the coast of Fyn, Denmark. Knowing the impact of grazers on an ecosystem helps us comprehend the intricate relationships between organisms, nutrient cycling, vegetation dynamics, and overall ecosystem health. This knowledge is vital for making informed decisions regarding conservation, land management, and sustainable resource utilization (Côté et al., 2004). This project serves as preparation for a subsequent Master's Thesis where I will examine the diet of the animals in order to understand the impact they have on the island's ecosystem. The project is being conducted in collaboration with the Aage v. Jensen Foundation, which owns and manages the island and is dedicated to supporting this research endeavor. In the project's initial phase, I focus on gaining an in-depth understanding of the research area and familiarizing myself with the foundation's existing management plan. By understanding the intricacies of the island and the foundation's conservation efforts, I aim to develop comprehensive insights into the challenges posed by grazers and their influence on the local ecosystem. This preliminary investigation will guide us in formulating a research question, which will be further explored and addressed in the subsequent Master's Thesis. Furthermore, an essential aspect of this project involves the development of a methodology to analyze the grazers' diet through eDNA (environmental DNA) analysis. This innovative approach allows us to examine the genetic material left behind by grazers in their surroundings, providing valuable insights into their dietary preferences and patterns. As part of this project I will undertake extensive fieldwork on Æbelø, collecting samples for subsequent laboratory analysis which I will continue into my Master's Thesis. It allows me to develop and clarify an adaptable sampling strategy during the process and sample across 8 months to gain a temporal understanding of the effects of fallow deer and mouflons on Æbelø. In addition to eDNA analysis, alternative methods for assessing the impact of grazers on woodland ecosystems are explored in this project. By incorporating a multi-faceted approach, I can comprehensively evaluate the pressure exerted by grazers on the island's delicate ecological balance. Through this thorough exploration of methodologies, I aim to contribute to the wider body of knowledge on grazing effects and provide valuable recommendations for sustainable management practices. By undertaking this project, I aim to deepen our understanding of the specific challenges Æbelø faces and contribute to the broader field of ecological research. The findings from this project will serve as a foundation for the subsequent Master's Thesis, which will delve into the identified research question in greater detail.

Methods

Research Area

Æbelø is a small island located North of Fyn, Denmark (see Fig. 1). It covers an area of 2,32 km² and has been uninhabited since 2009. Æbelø is connected to Æbeløholm by a 1.5 km long, narrow isthmus, Brådet, which like Æbelø, is a marine foreland formed by beach embankment deposits of sand, gravel, and pebbles (Nabe-Nielsen et al., 2022). Material is constantly eroding from the island's cliffs by wave erosion since their formation. Æbeløholm, separated from Fyn by a tidal flat approximately 1 km wide, becomes accessible on foot or by a tractor during low tide. The island's composition primarily consists of moraine clay and meltwater sand, though several areas reveal older deposits such as Palaeocene plastic clay along the coastal slopes. Peat and freshwater sand deposits can be found in the island's central region, while marine pebble ramparts are present towards the southern part near Brådet.

Figure 1: The island Æbelø located north of Fyn in Denmark (© Google)

Æbelø, unlike other small Danish islands, stands out for its predominantly forested landscape, suggesting lower historical human population density and utilization. While there is limited information about its history, it is believed that the island has been inhabited for extended periods, though historical records are scarce. The earliest documented accounts of Æbelø date back to the late Middle Ages. From the late 15th century, timber was harvested from the island for construction and fuel, likely by both local farmers and landowners. The island served as grazing land for horses and, from the 1500s, for cattle as well. Fallow deer were likely introduced to the island during the late Middle Ages. While not permanently inhabited during this period, Æbelø experienced activity during the summer, attracting fishing for herring and cod. Until 1578, Æbelø was under royal jurisdiction, managed by various local lords. Following that, the island remained in noble ownership until 1623,

when the citizens of Bogense were granted permission to purchase it. Around 1650, Æbelø saw permanent residents who engaged in year-round living, combining fishing with agriculture. However, agriculture on the island was limited. Growing grain intensively for commercial purposes was not profitable due to high transport costs, and historical sources indicate that the island remained predominantly forested (Nabe-Nielsen et al., 2022).

In recent times, with changing ownership of the island, some of the fields were converted into tree plantations, renewing the emphasis on hunting and forestry on the island. By 1845, Æbelø was home to five households engaging in fishing, farming, forestry, and sawmilling. During the 1900s, hunting and forestry became even more prominent on the island. Agriculture shifted towards supporting hunting interests, with a particular focus on fallow deer and pheasants. Descriptions from the 1940s highlight the high population densities of roe deer and fallow deer, resulting in the suppression of undergrowth, a characteristic still observable in the island's forests today.

In 1995, the private environmental foundation Aage V. Jensen Naturfond bought Æbelø and the neighboring islands. In 1999 the area was placed under nature conservation. The preservation confirmed Aage V. Jensen Nature Foundation's wish to "support the dynamics and diversity of nature during the property's development from cultivated agriculture to the untouched forest". The preservation thus protects the island's forests from forestry, which had been intensified before the foundation took over the property in 1995. In addition, the preservation includes provisions for the clearing of introduced conifers, restoration of hydrology, and the cessation of active agriculture, except for the continued mowing of part of the plains. Æbelø is under strict nature protection through Danish law and the Natura 2000 project. The foundation's goal is the establishment of a natural forest without any interference in the process. The challenge the foundation faces in reaching that target is the high number of grazers inhabiting the island. There is a herd of approximately 20 mouflons (*Ovis aries musimon*) and a lot of fallow deer (*Dama dama*), around 700 animals. The exact amount is hard to estimate as the fallow deer migrates from Fyn to the island during low tide. That makes the management of the animals very challenging. The current management strategy is culling the animals once a year in autumn. According to the local manager Sanne Frederiksen (personal communication, n.d.), that seems to be fruitless, as the deer simply leave the island once they figure out that it is being hunted, and the population is reinforced with animals from Fyn after the hunting season is over. This project is set to find out the exact diets of the animals from April to October to understand their dietary preferences and the pressure they put on the ecosystem. With almost a year-round diet observation, the foundation can then develop a sustainable management plan for the grazers on Æbelø.

eDNA

Advancements in eDNA metabarcoding offer a versatile approach to studying the dietary preferences of herbivores, overcoming the limitations of traditional methods. By analyzing fecal samples, this technique provides an alternative means to reconstruct diets accurately. Its efficacy has already been demonstrated characterizing diet in a variety of animal species, including deer, bison, moose, and horses. Furthermore, eDNA metabarcoding holds immense potential for investigating the impacts of species on natural habitats and biodiversity. To illustrate its applicability, this project will examine a specific study conducted in Denmark that employed this method to assess seasonal variations in plant diets among co-existing feral cattle and horses.

Assessment of herbivore impact

To evaluate the influence of fallow deer and mouflons on the vegetation of Æbelø, I have opted to employ "The Woodland Herbivore Impact Assessment Method." Developed by Armstrong et al. (2020), this method facilitates assessing and monitoring large herbivore impacts on woodland habitats or areas susceptible to woodland growth. Unlike precise measurements, this method relies mainly on observations. The provided guide offers several approaches for evaluating the impact. In my study, I have chosen to focus on assessing the woodland structure and examining historical herbivore impact. In some instances, prolonged high browsing or grazing pressure can eradicate most indicators of current herbivore impacts. Thus, assessing longer-term effects (spanning a decade or more) becomes valuable using different indicators. As the mouflon and deer have been on the island for over 20 years, it made sense to select these methods. Additionally, investigating past impact is pertinent to this project, which primarily encompasses the summer months, as the current herbivore impact is most noticeable during early spring.

Results

Protocol

In the course of the project, various methodologies were explored with the aim of addressing the research question. The primary approach adopted for investigating the dietary habits of Fallow deer and mouflons on Æbelø was modeled on the technique developed by Thomassen et al. (2022). This involved the collection of fecal samples from both species over a period of several months, which were then subjected to eDNA analysis. The analysis enables determining the animals' feeding behavior and estimating the resulting browsing pressure exerted on the island.

Fieldwork

The first step was the creation of a sampling protocol for the data collection. It was decided to sample every month from April to October 2023. Ideally, the sampling period would be 3 days at the end of each month. It was then decided to designate 5 collection areas on the island (see Fig. 2), which was done on the first field trip (Beginning of May) with the help of the project manager Sanne Frederiksen.

Figure 2: This figure shows the different collection areas on the island. The five original ones (A-E) are marked in blue. The first modification B* is marked in orange, the second one EF* and EM* are marked in yellow.

Five samples from each species, fallow deer and mouflon, will be collected in these five areas. The feces can be differentiated by their structure. While fallow deer excrete mostly many small pellets, the mouflon's dung is one coherent pile. The first idea, to pool these five samples, was dropped after

consultation with Philip Thomsen to avoid biases (e.g., losing the information on individual variation). It was then decided to rather take five subsamples in each sample and pool these. In summary, in each area, five samples (individual dung piles) from each species were taken, and each of these samples consisted of five subsamples from the same dung pile. That makes a total of 50 samples per each of the seven field trips. These are 350 samples in total. Due to the cost of the eDNA analysis, it was decided only to analyze one sample per area per species. That gives a total of 70 samples over the course of the data collection.

Summarized sample collection protocol:

1. Sampling period: 3 days from April to October (ideally at the end of the month)
2. 5 designated collection areas on the island
3. 5 samples per area per species
4. One sample consists of five subsamples

For the collection of the feces, the following protocol was developed:

1. Find a fresh dung pellet in the area.
2. Take the GPS location and a picture
3. Put on nitrile gloves for the sampling process (use a new pair for every area)
4. Use a plastic toothpick (change after every subsample -> subsamples are the samples from the same individual (see step 6)) and a plastic knife/spoon/fork (change after five samples) to collect the sample
5. The knife/spoon/fork is used to open the pellet, while the plastic toothpick is used to scrape out the dung's core and put it in a 1,5 ml Eppendorf tube.
6. Change the toothpick, rinse the plastic cutlery with water, and repeat that last process a total of 5 times for the same sample. Pool all five subsamples in the same tube.
7. Repeat the whole process five times per species per area (giving us approximately samples from 5 individuals)
8. In the end, per area, I will have sampled feces from 5 individuals from each of the species during each visit

During the first field trip, I came across the problem that one of the areas (B) did not prove to be suitable for the collection of samples, so I chose a different area (B*) based on my observations in the field. During the second field trip, area E proved to be very difficult to find any samples in, which is why I decided to drop this area and select two new ones, split up as one area for fallow deer (EF*) and one area for mouflon (EM*). During the third field trip, it was very difficult to find any samples, especially for mouflon, so I decided to let go of the selected areas for mouflon and try to find 10-25 good samples regardless of the sampling areas.

To further assess the impact of the herbivores on Æbelø, the island's woodland structures and the historic browsing pressure were examined following Armstrong et al. (2020). Their guide "Assessing Herbivore Impact in Woodlands: An Observation-based Method" presents several methods that can be used to assess and monitor the impact of large herbivores on woodlands. In this study, it was decided to assess the historic browsing pressure and the woodland structure, which is a good indicator of the habitat condition. The following protocol was developed:

1. Select 10 random sites on the island
2. Mark the GPS location
3. Take photographs in each cardinal direction, from the forest floor and the canopy
4. Compare the pictures to the guide to assess the pressure

Lab-work

During the project, the methodology for the eDNA analysis was developed. The following Figure 3 shows the different steps that are needed in order to analyze the feces of the animals for their diet preferences.

Figure 3: Different steps of the eDNA-barcoding in order to analyze the diet of the fallow deer and mouflon on *Æbelø*. Protocols that were tested in this preparation project are highlighted in green.

The first step, the eDNA extraction, is carried out after each sampling period. The Qiagen DNeasy® Plant Pro Kit was used to extract the eDNA. It also came with an extraction protocol, which was

followed during the extraction with slight modifications from my co-supervisor Kasun Bodawatta. The samples were first homogenized with 600 µl of nuclease-free water (following Thomassen et al., 2022) in order to ensure full homogenization of the partly dry dung. After a second homogenization process in the TissueLyzer II, the samples are put in a rotor and placed in an oven at 56°C for one hour to facilitate the chemical lysing process. The EB buffer (elution buffer) was heated up to 37°C before usage in order to increase its binding affinity. After adding the EB buffer, the spin columns were heated again at 37°C for 5 minutes before the last step of the DNA extraction to facilitate the binding of EB to DNA on the membrane (Bodawatta, K., personal communication, n.d.). The full protocol, with modifications in yellow, is shown in Table 1.

In total, three sets of samples that were gathered in early May (01.-03.05.23), late May (30.-31.05.23), and June (21.06.23) were processed in the laboratory during this project period. The final results of the eDNA analysis will be part of the subsequent Master's Thesis, where I aim to analyze seven sample sets, across seven months.

After the three extractions, a qPCR was done to monitor the success of the DNA extraction process but also to test how many PCR cycles are needed for tag PCRs, as too many cycles increase the amplification biases. Another reason for the qPCR is to test for inhibition. If too much DNA is in the sample, the reaction could get inhibited. For this we conducted the qPCR with 4 different DNA concentrations to find out which dilution works best with the samples. That way, other possible inhibition factors can be canceled out, too. The protocol for the qPCR can be found in Table 2. Tables 3 and 4 show the instructions for the Master Mix that was used and the Primer testing setup. The primers used for the qPCR: Forward: Trac01 (GATATCCRTTGCCGAGAGTC), and Reverse: ITS-7A (GAAGGAGAAGTCGTAACAAGG) (Taberlet et al., 2018).

Table 1: Protocol for the DNA extraction from DNeasy® Plant Pro Kit with additions in yellow.

		Laboratory Protocol DNA extraction											
Pre-working steps	Step 1	Step 2	Step 3	Step 4	Step 5	Step 6	Step 7	Step 8	Step 9	Step 10	Step 11	Step 12	
Add ethanol to Buffer AW1 and AW2 (only if precipitated after a while)	Put EB buffer in a heatblock at 37 °C	Add 600 µl of nuclease-free water to the sample and vortex for 10-20 sec per side to homogenize the sample	~100 mg plant tissue + 500 µl CD1 to 2 ml tissue disruption tube. Vortex briefly	Homogenize in TissueLyser II at 24 Hz for 2 mins per side	Incubate for an hour at 56 °C	Centrifuge at 12,000 x g for 2 min	Transfer supernatant to clean 1.5 ml microcentrifuge tube	Add 250 µl CD2, vortex 5 s x g for 1 min	Centrifuge at 12,000 x g for 1 min	Transfer supernatant to clean 1.5 ml microcentrifuge tube (avoid the pellet)	Add 500 µl APP and vortex 5 s	Load 600 µl lysate to MB Spin Column	
Heat Buffer APB at 60 °C until dissolved if precipitated													
	Step 13	Step 14	Step 15	Step 16	Step 17	Step 18	Step 19	Step 20	Step 21	Step 22	Step 23	Step 24	
	Centrifuge for at 12,000 x g for 1 min	Discard flow-through, repeat centrifuge	Place MB spin column into a clean 2 ml collection tube	Add 650 µl AW1	Centrifuge at 12,000 x g for 1 min	Discard flow-through and place MB spin column back to same tube	Add 650 µl AW2 and centrifuge at 12,000 x g for 1 min	Discard flow-through and place MB spin column in same tube	Centrifuge at up to 16,000 x g for 2 min. Place MB spin column into new 1.5 ml tube	Add 100 µl EB to center of membrane.	Incubate for 5 mins at 37 °C	Centrifuge at 12,000 x g for 1 min. Discard spin column.	

Table 2: Protocol for the qPCR of 6 selected samples (2 from each field trip).

Laboratory protocol qPCR				
Step 1	Step 2	Step 3	Step 4	Step 5
Make the Master Mix	Put 23µl of Master Mix in the PCR tubes	Create the dilution 1:2, 1:5, 1:10 with water and the selected DNA samples	Add 2 µl of DNA or dilutions to the PCR tubes with the Master Mix	Run the qPCR

Table 3: Instructions for the creation of the Master Mix for the qPCR.

Master Mix for qPCR											
	DNA	Gold PCR buffer	MgCl2	DNTP	Tag gold	BSA	SYBR	H2O	Primer F	Primer R	
Initial concentration		10	x	25	mM	10	mM	5	units/µl	20	mg/ml
Final concentration in each 20		1	x	2.5	mM	0.2	mM	1	units	0.5	mg/ml
µl for 1 rxn	2	2.5 µl	2.5 µl	0.5 µl	0.2 µl	0.625 µl	1 µl	12.675	1.5 µl	1.5 µl	Final volume for 1 rxn
RXNS	40	100 µl	100 µl	20 µl	8 µl	25 µl	40 µl	507	60	60	25 µl
add a few samples more to mastermix											
To add to mastermix for qPCR											

Table 4: Primer testing setup for the qPCR. 4 different dilutions (neat, 1:2, 1:5 and 1:10) for 6 selected samples from DNA extraction.

Primer testing setup qPCR				
Project:	Trac01 primers Æbelø			
Date:	06.07.2023			
Dilutions:	2µl (Neat) of DNA, 1:2, 1:5, 1:10			
Notes:	Positive used was possible Alder seed			
Name:	Kasun and Henry			
Trac01	Henry			
	25ul			
Dilutions	Neat	01:02	01:05	01:10
	1	2	3	4
A	BF2	BF2_1_2	BF2_1_5	BF2_1_10
B	DM1	DM1_1_2	DM1_1_5	DM1_1_10
C	A2_M4	A2_M4_1_2	A2_M4_1_5	A2_M4_1_10
D	E2_F1	E2_F1_1_2	E2_F1_1_5	E2_F1_1_10
E	A3_M1	A3_M1_1_2	A3_M1_1_5	A3_M1_1_10
F	C3_F1	C3_F1_1_2	C3_F1_1_5	C3_F1_1_10
G	UX	UX_1_2	UX_1_5	UX_1_10
H	qPCR bl	qPCR bl	qPCR bl	qPCR bl
POS= Alder seed possibly				
Parameters				
Trac01 primers (Plants)				
95C	10 mins			
95C	30 sec	50		
56C	30 sec			
72C	30 sec			
Dis.curve				

The results of the qPCR are shown in Figure 4. In the pictures, the amplifications of the samples, as well as the dissociation curves, can be seen. All samples have been amplified after 26 cycles at the most, confirming the presence of plant DNA in the samples. The dissociation curves also do not show any complications regarding amplification or inhibition in the samples. The curve of the positive used

in the qPCR (identified as an Alder seed) is shown in purple. The odd curves (yellow) belong to the extraction blank (water) that were used and are evidence for primer dimers.

Figure 4:

A-D: Shows the amplification curves of the samples. All samples have been amplified after 26 cycles at most.

E-H: Dissociation curves of the samples. The curves show good results and no inhibition or amplification problems. The curves standing out belong to the extraction blanks.

Assessment of herbivore impact

In the following, I carried out a woodland structure assessment after Armstrong et al. (2020) on Æbelø. Over the three field trips, I visited 31 random sites on the island and took pictures to compare them to the 10 woodland structure classes identified by Armstrong et al. (2020) in their guide to assess herbivore impacts in woodland. Structure classes 1 and 2 are open-ground habitats, classes 3 to 8 are native woodland habitats, and 9 and 10 are wood pasture and parkland habitats. The figures showing the different woodland structure classes can be found in Appendix 1-10. Figure 6 shows one of the sites and the best comparison. The rest of the pictures can be found in Appendix 11-41. Table 5 then summarizes all the comparisons.

Figure 6: A-F shows the pictures taken in the field on Æbelø. They show an old-growth forest with no new growth, a grassy forest floor, and a relatively dense canopy.

G-I shows the comparable woodland structure class 6 with a similar pattern.

Table 5: Assessment of the woodland structure classes of the 32 visited sites on Æbelø.

Woodland structure class								
Location	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
Structure class	8	6	6	4	6	6	6	6
Location	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16
Structure class	6	8	4	6	6	6	6	8
Location	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24
Structure class	6	5	6	6	6	6	6	6
Location	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32
Structure class	6	10	6	6	8	5	4	6

The most common woodland structure class identified was class 6. Armstrong et al. (2020) define this habitat class as mature woodland without any understory regeneration. This description refers to mature woodland areas characterized by small gaps in the canopy or limited competition among the taller trees. These forests typically have a single layer of fully grown trees with few or no smaller trees beneath them. The understory is either sparse or absent, and the ground layer consists of short vegetation composed of unpalatable species like bracken or purple moor grass. There are few to no woody plants present in these areas. These features indicate that the woodland has likely experienced moderate to heavy impacts from herbivores in the past. This is consistent with the baseline reports and the observations made in the field.

I furthermore decided also to assess the historic herbivore impact on the island as the grazing pressure has been so high for such a long time that indicators of current impacts may have been eliminated. To do that, I used the guide by Armstrong et al. (2020), which provides an explanation of high, medium, low, and absent impact for different woodland types. Comparing the descriptions to the pictures taken and the observations made in the field, I came to the result that Æbelø has been under high grazing pressure for at least 10 years.

Discussion

Fieldwork

Development of the sampling protocol proved to be effective during the initial three field trips to Æbelø. As anticipated, the qPCR results confirmed the presence of plant DNA in the samples, providing me with information needed for conducting the tag PCRs for metabarcoding. However, the selection of sampling areas encountered some challenges and required modifications, as outlined in the results. The first change, shifting from area B to B*, became necessary due to the inaccessibility of the initially chosen location and the absence of dung. B* was selected as an alternative, considering it as a large, open grass area where deer and mouflon sightings were prominent during the initial field trip.

Another adjustment was made during the second collection period, transitioning from area E to EF* and EM*. This change was prompted by the inability to find any dung in area E, which had become significantly overgrown with grass. EF* and EM* were selected based on the observation of respective animals in these areas during previous field trips. On the third field trip, finding dung became particularly challenging, and animal sightings were noticeably scarce compared to previous visits. This could be attributed to a preceding heat wave, resulting in dry habitat conditions that potentially led the animals to relocate to Fyn, where food sources might be more abundant. It is also possible that the animals exhibited seasonal behavioral changes or temporarily left the island, factors which were not initially considered.

Considering the small population size of mouflon (20 individuals) in contrast to the fallow deer (maximum 700), I have concluded that a change in the sample collection approach is necessary. I will maintain the sample collection areas A, B*, C, D, and EF* for the fallow deer. However, I will discontinue using specific areas for the mouflon. Instead, I will treat the entire island as a unified sampling area and aim to collect 10-25 samples for the mouflon during each field trip. This adjustment should prevent returning empty-handed in case no dung is found in the designated areas while minimizing the introduction of significant bias.

Lab-work

In the lab, the eDNA analysis methods were shown to me by my co-supervisor, Kasun Bodawatta. For this preparatory project, my involvement primarily focused on DNA extraction and conducting qPCR, while the remaining steps will be carried out once all samples are collected. The DNA

extraction process proceeded as planned, following the user-friendly protocol provided by the DNeasy® Plant Pro Kit. Kasun Bodawatta made some necessary adjustments to accommodate the specific sample material we were working with, and these modifications proved effective based on the qPCR results obtained.

The results clearly indicate the presence of plant DNA in the samples I collected. However, the analysis does not provide detailed information regarding the number of different plant species present. Additionally, it was observed that the DNA amplifies after 26 cycles during the qPCR. Consequently, the subsequent Tag PCR step will only require 26 PCR cycles, minimizing the introduction of biases associated with additional amplification cycles (Bodawatta, K., personal communication, n.d.).

Furthermore, based on the evaluation of six randomly selected samples, it was determined that a dilution of 1:2 yielded the most favorable outcomes. Therefore, I will proceed with this dilution for the subsequent stages of the metabarcoding.

Assessment of herbivore impacts

To assess the impact of herbivores on Æbelø, I opted to utilize the guide titled "Assessing Herbivore Impact in Woodlands: An Observation-based Method" by Armstrong et al. (2020) in conjunction with the eDNA analysis. It should be noted that this method relies on subjective observations rather than precise measurements. Observers are required to carefully assess the overall appearance of the habitat and take note of specific indicators within it. This inherent subjectivity introduces an observer bias that may have influenced the results, especially considering that I am the sole person conducting the assessment.

Additionally, it is important to acknowledge that the guide is based on habitats in Scotland, which may yield slightly different outcomes compared to the specific species found in Denmark. However, the findings of the woodland structure class analysis aligned with expectations. The primary class identified indicated mature woodland with a lack of understory regeneration, indicating high herbivore pressure. This observation corresponds to what is evident on the island and is further supported by the pictures provided in the appendix. These results are consistent with previous reports and statements from the foundation responsible for managing the island.

Unfortunately, I neglected to mark the GPS location of some photographed areas on three occasions, rendering them unidentifiable on the map. Furthermore, certain pictures may appear blurry due to irreparable technical issues with the camera on my phone.

Regarding the assessment of historic herbivore impact, the results are in agreement with previous reports, indicating prolonged high grazing pressure for at least a decade. While it would have been desirable to evaluate the current herbivore impacts on Æbelø, Armstrong et al. (2020) recommend conducting assessments at the end of winter before new spring growth begins, particularly if grazing occurs year-round and the objective is to gauge overall grazing pressure. Since our assessment took place in late spring/early summer, I decided to rely on the historical herbivore impact. The sustained high pressure on Æbelø throughout the years may render the current impact difficult to detect for untrained observers.

The Thesis preparation project served as an excellent first step toward the completion of my Master's Thesis. It provided me with in-depth knowledge and valuable insights into the research area and methodologies involved. The developed sampling protocol is not only comprehensible but also flexible, allowing for adjustments in the event of unforeseen circumstances. Moreover, the DNA extraction protocol proved to be successful, as evidenced by the positive qPCR results. This important initial phase has laid a solid foundation for my forthcoming Thesis, which aims to investigate the dietary preferences of herbivores on Æbelø. Ultimately, this research project will contribute to a deeper understanding of the ecosystem and aid in its sustainable management.

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Appendix

Appendix 1

Appendix 1: Woodland structure class 1 (Armstrong et al., 2020)

Appendix 2

Appendix 2: Woodland structure class 2 (Armstrong et al., 2020)

Appendix 3

Appendix 3: Woodland structure class 3 (Armstrong et al., 2020)

Appendix 4

Appendix 4: Woodland structure class 4 (Armstrong et al., 2020)

Appendix 5

Appendix 5: Woodland structure class 5 (Armstrong et al., 2020)

Appendix 6

Appendix 6: Woodland structure class 6 (Armstrong et al., 2020)

Appendix 7

Appendix 7: Woodland structure class 7 (Armstrong et al., 2020)

Appendix 8

Appendix 8: Woodland structure class 8 (Armstrong et al., 2020)

Appendix 9

Appendix 9: Woodland structure class 9 (Armstrong et al., 2020)

Appendix 10

Appendix 10: Woodland structure class 10 (Armstrong et al., 2020)

Appendix 11

Appendix 11: Pictures of the woodland structure of location 1

Appendix 12

Appendix 12: Pictures of the woodland structure of location 2

Appendix 13

Appendix 13: Pictures of the woodland structure of location 3

Appendix 14

Appendix 14: Pictures of the woodland structure of location 4

Appendix 15

Appendix 15: Pictures of the woodland structure of location 5

Appendix 16

Appendix 16: Pictures of the woodland structure of location 6

Appendix 17

Appendix 17: Pictures of the woodland structure of location 7

Appendix 18

Appendix 18: Pictures of the woodland structure of location 8

Appendix 19

Appendix 19: Pictures of the woodland structure of location 9

Appendix 20

Appendix 20: Pictures of the woodland structure of location 10

Appendix 21

Appendix 21: Pictures of the woodland structure of location 11

Appendix 22

Appendix 22: Pictures of the woodland structure of location 12

Appendix 23

Appendix 23: Pictures of the woodland structure of location 13

Appendix 24

Appendix 24: Pictures of the woodland structure of location 14

Appendix 25

Appendix 25: Pictures of the woodland structure of location 15

Appendix 26

Appendix 26: Pictures of the woodland structure of location 16

Appendix 27

Appendix 27: Pictures of the woodland structure of location 17

Appendix 28

Appendix 28: Pictures of the woodland structure of location 18

Appendix 29

Appendix 29: Pictures of the woodland structure of location 19

Appendix 30

Appendix 30: Pictures of the woodland structure of location 20

Appendix 31

Appendix 31: Pictures of the woodland structure of location 21

Appendix 32

Appendix 32: Pictures of the woodland structure of location 22

Appendix 33

Appendix 33: Pictures of the woodland structure of location 23

Appendix 34

Appendix 34: Pictures of the woodland structure of location 24

Appendix 35

Appendix 35: Pictures of the woodland structure of location 25

Appendix 36

Appendix 36: Pictures of the woodland structure of location 26

Appendix 37

Appendix 37: Pictures of the woodland structure of location 27

Appendix 38

Appendix 38: Pictures of the woodland structure of location 28

Appendix 39

Appendix 39: Pictures of the woodland structure of location 29

Appendix 40

Appendix 40: Pictures of the woodland structure of location 30

Appendix 41

Appendix 41: Pictures of the woodland structure of location 31

